

TACTICAL FEATURES OF FORENSIC EXAMINATION DURING THE INVESTIGATION OF CRIMES RELATED TO VIOLATIONS OF TRAFFIC RULES AND VEHICLE OPERATION

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6259316>

Mullajonov Ilhomjon Vasiyjonovich

*Head of the Department of Medical Forensics of the Fergana branch of
the Republican Scientific-Practical Center of Forensic Medicine*

Madazimov Farhod Sadirovich

*Republican Scientific-Practical Center of Forensic Medicine Fergana
Branch Margilon District Department Head: State Forensic Medical Expert*

Vasijonov Abduboqi Ikromjon ugli

Student of the Faculty of Military Education of FerSU

Annotatoin: *The author examines the opinions of scientists on the appointment of forensic examination, its importance for the investigating crimes related to violation of traffic rules and operation of vehicles.*

Keywords: *forensic examination, a comprehensive auto-technical and forensic examination.*

Taking into account modern practice of investigation of crimes connected with violation of traffic rules and operation of vehicles and arising problems formulated theoretical conclusions and practical recommendations aimed at increasing the effectiveness of the use of special knowledge as a means of obtaining investigative and evidentiary information.

During investigation a special place in the system of investigative actions is taken by appointment of a forensic examination. During investigation of crimes related to violations of traffic rules and operation of vehicles practically all types of expertise are appointed: forensic, criminological, forensic-autotechnical, roadside and others.

In addition to technical expertise, during the investigation of crimes related to violations of the rules of road traffic and operation of vehicles forensic examination is appointed to establish the severity of injury to health, causes of bodily injury or death. Forensic examination is governed by Order No.6 of the Ministry of Health and Social Development, dated 27 June 2007, “On judicial practice in cases involving intentional bodily harm”.

Forensic medical examination is an expert study, which gives an opinion on issues of medical and biological nature related to the vital functions and functions of the human body. Its decision, judging from literary sources, relevant rulings, and studied criminal cases, is based on the following questions:

- Does this person have any injuries, and if so, what is their nature, number, and localization?
- With what object and in what way was the person injured?
- Were the injuries sustained by the person in the circumstances and at the time indicated by the person? If not, under what circumstances could they have been sustained?
- What is the age of the injuries sustained by the victim and does the victim's testimony about the age of the injuries correspond to objective data?
- Were the injuries sustained at the same time or at different times?
- What is the severity of the person's injuries?
- Are the injuries permanent?
- What is the duration of the impairment of the person's health due to the injuries?
- Are the injuries related to the infliction of special physical pain on the victim?

It is noted that when preparing materials for the forensic medical examination, the investigator, first of all, retrieves medical history, outpatient records, X-rays. If the necessary information is missing, it is necessary to question the doctor on duty, the surgeon, the attending physician, consultant doctors, to ensure the examination of the patient. It is noted that it is also necessary to submit medical documents, records of interrogations of doctors, other witnesses and the accused whose testimony is connected with the questions put to the expert.

Sometimes, in addition to the victims, suspects, witnesses with bodily injuries. In the examination of a corpse, it is noted, the following general questions are addressed:

- What is the sex, age, and height of the deceased?
- What is the cause of death?
- When did death occur?
- What were the injuries on the corpse (their number, nature, location) and what could have caused them?
- Which injuries were inflicted while the deceased was alive and which after death?

- What kind or type of weapon caused the wounds?
- What was the direction and length of the wound channel, size of the injury?
- What is the severity and age of each injury?
- Which of the injuries inflicted on the victim were fatal?
- Is there a direct causal link between the injury and one or another external impact and death?
- What is the most probable mutual position of the victim at the time of the injuries that were incompatible with life?

With regard to transportation and automobile trauma, as noted, the forensic examination of the corpse also allows us to answer such specific questions:

- Are the injuries found on the corpse characteristic of a motor vehicle injury? If yes, by what mode of transport could they have been caused?
- What is the nature and location of the injuries on the clothing and body?
- At what level from the soles of the deceased are these injuries located?
- Were all of the injuries observed in the examination of the corpse sustained at the same time or at different times?

If the injuries were sustained at different times, were there two collisions?

- What is the mechanism of formation of the injuries (impact, body falling on the ground, wheel rolling over the victim with subsequent running over)?
- Where is the location of the traumatic force and what is its direction?
- Do the location and nature of the injuries on the victim's body correspond to the injuries found on the victim's clothing and shoes?

To find out exactly what parts of the vehicle were damaged, a comprehensive auto and forensic examination is appointed. If there was a collision between the car and the victim, the complex auto-technical and forensic examination allows to establish:

- What injuries resulted from the direct impact with parts of the moving vehicle? What injuries were caused by the subsequent fall (from the impact and friction against the ground)?
- From which side (left, right, front, rear) and in which direction in relation to the victim was the protruding part of the vehicle hit?
- In what position was the victim in relation to the moving vehicle at the time of impact and subsequent fall?

- What is the possible sequence of injuries sustained in the collision with the car? Were they sustained at the same time or at different times?

- Which part of the moving vehicle (bumper, radiator, headlight, running board, bodywork, etc.) was hit? Could this part of the vehicle (say make of vehicle) have caused the damage?

If there was a run over with a wheel (army) of the car, the complex auto-technical and forensic examination allows to answer the following questions:

- Was the vehicle loaded or unloaded?

- From which side and in which direction in relation to the victim's body was the crossing performed?

- In what position was the victim in at the moment of crossing with the wheel (armies) of the car?

- Which wheels (front, rear, right, left) and in what order was the victim's body crossed?

If there was an injury (passengers, driver) in the cabin of the car when it collided with some obstacle, also notes, complex auto-technical and forensic examination allows to answer the following questions:

- Which injuries were caused by the impact on the parts of the cabin and the concussion of the body, and which ones were caused by squeezing of the body due to its displaced parts (cabin, bodywork)?

- In which seats (front, back) in the car cabin were any of the victims, in particular, which of them was sitting behind the wheel at the time of the accident?

A lot of important information for forensic examination is contained in the protocols of the scene examination, in particular those concerning the description of the corpse and vehicles. The results of other investigative actions (investigative experiments, examination of victims, protocols of interrogations of victims, witnesses, accused, as well as information from the conclusions of other examinations) are also used during the examination.

In order to address the questions posed, the investigator should allow the forensic expert to examine the victim, review his medical history and study his X-rays, provide for examination the clothing in which the victim was at the time of the accident, allow the expert to examine the vehicle that committed the hit and run, and in some cases travel with the expert to inspect the scene.

During forensic examinations, it is recommended to use photographs and video recordings from the examination of the scene of the accident and other investigative actions. If a forensic examination of a corpse is

conducted, it is recommended to send to the expert: case files relating to the examination, seizure, and storage of objects of examination; acts of forensic examination of living persons and forensic autopsies, examination of the corpse; protocols of the examination of the scene, investigative experiments; documents reflecting changes in the objects, expert examination since seizure up to the moment of submission for examination; and protocols containing actual forensic medical data.

The following are sent for expert examination: an ambulatory chart, protocol of pathological-anatomical examination, protocols of clinical-anatomical conference, results of departmental investigation, medical history and other medical documents (dental records, certificates and certificates of medical commissions, etc.), all clothing of the victim (with all damages and overlays).

At appointment of all types of forensic examinations, professionally competent formulation of questions demanding the permission and preparation of materials of expert examination is of basic importance. The help of experts is extremely important in this respect.

For this purpose, it seems appropriate to carry out preventive work aimed at eliminating the causes and conditions that contribute to the commission of this category of crimes.

Availability of necessary skills and abilities for committing the specified crime, its full-fledged investigation and subsequently delivering just and reasonable verdict in court is an indisputable factor.

Thus, forensic examination in the investigation of crimes related to violations of traffic rules and operation of vehicles acts as one of the certain means of proof, and its effectiveness is largely predetermined by the results of the activity of specialists contributing to the detection, fixation and seizure of traces of crime.

LIST OF THE USED LITERATURE:

1. Gainelazhnova V. R. The use of special knowledge in investigation of crimes related to violation of the rules of road traffic and operation of vehicles: doctoral dissertation.

of means: abstract of the dissertation. D. in law. Chelyabinsk, 2012.

2. Order of Ministry of Health and Social Development of the RepUz from 27 June, 2007. № 6 " On judicial practice in cases involving intentional bodily harm".

4. Popov V.L. Forensic-medical expertise of severity of harm to health: textbook-biography. Saint-Petersburg, 1999.

5. <https://cyberleninka.ru/article/n/takticheskie-osobennosti-naznacheniya-sudebno-meditsinskoy-ekspertizy-pri-rassledovanii-prestupleniy-svyazannyh-s-narusheniem-pravil>